

Results from statistical analysis (P values) of effects of experiment, CO₂, and density on rice and barnyard grass (BYG). The density comparisons are for 1 vs 8 plants/pot (only intraspecific competition) and 1 vs all multiple plants (2-8)/pot (includes interspecific competition).

Source	df	Tiller no.		Leaf no.		Leaf dry weight		Stem dry weight		Total dry weight	
		Rice	BYG	Rice	BYG	Rice	BYG	Rice	BYG	Rice	BYG
Experiment	1	0.14	0.04	0.36	0.03	0.02	0.04	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.01
Block	2	0.07	0.79	0.10	0.43	0.05	0.47	0.08	0.07	0.12	0.05
CO ₂	3	0.05	0.42	0.04	0.48	0.12	0.29	0.08	0.18	0.16	0.01
Experiment × CO ₂	3	0.33	0.52	0.27	0.11	0.12	0.25	0.19	0.56	0.16	0.92
Density (1 vs 8 plants)	4	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.11	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
(1 vs 2-8 plants)	1	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01
Experiment × density	4	0.08	0.34	0.36	<0.01	<0.01	<0.01	0.03	0.07	0.01	0.22
CO ₂ × density	12	<0.01	0.43	<0.01	0.88	<0.01	0.50	0.07	0.66	0.06	0.62
Chamber (Experiment × CO ₂)	7	0.09	0.38	0.28	0.85	0.40	0.48	0.11	0.24	0.07	0.52
Error	124	(123 for leaf dry weight)									
Total	159	(158 for leaf dry weight)									

eters ($P < 0.01$), largely because of the increase in growth at 1 plant/pot vs other densities.

Rice plants showed significant ($P < 0.05$) CO₂ × density interactions for leaf and tiller numbers and marginally significant interactions ($P = 0.06-0.07$) for stem and total shoot dry weight (see table). In terms of interspecific competition, rice tended to compete better with barnyard grass under elevated CO₂ levels compared with ambient CO₂; the mixtures with more rice and fewer barnyard grass plants per pot showed greater increases in growth (Fig. 1a). In terms of intraspecific competition, CO₂ stimulated rice plant growth more with one rice plant/pot compared with 8 plants/pot for all parameters.

As expected for C4 plants, barnyard grass showed no significant increase in

shoot growth with elevated CO₂, either with or without plant competition (see table), and there actually was a significant decrease in total dry weight primarily at low densities (Fig. 1b). Density by itself—across CO₂ levels—significantly affected all parameters except leaf dry weight ($P < 0.01$), with less growth when more plants were present in a pot.

Barnyard grass shoot growth did not show any significant (lowest $P = 0.43$) CO₂ × density interactions (see table), likely because of the lack of a general CO₂ response for this species. In terms of general competition, (across all CO₂ concentrations), barnyard grass growth tended to be less with more barnyard grass compared with rice plants in the mixtures. This (coupled with greater growth with 1 vs. 8 barnyard grass plants/pot) suggested

Effects of CO₂ and plant density on total shoot dry weight of a) rice and b) barnyard grass. Data are per plant and averages of eight plants, two from each of two experiments. Coefficients of variability across CO₂ levels, densities, and experiments were 44.7% for rice and 26.0% for barnyard grass.

that intraspecific competition among barnyard grass plants was more important than interspecific competition with rice. With increasing CO₂ concentrations, however, there was a trend toward decreased barnyard grass growth in the mixtures, suggesting that rice plants were becoming more competitive.

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A very simple model of crop growth: derivation and application

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Crop growth models are powerful tools to improve understanding of global climate change and to predict crop yield changes caused by these changes. The problem, however, is that models are often so complex that it is difficult to understand them. We have a very simple model (VSM) for determining crop growth. The

model can be written in only one line, hence it is easy to interpret the outputs.

Derivation of the VSM. The VSM is based on the following assumptions of crop growth processes:

1. The leaf area index (LAI) changes in a triangular pattern (see figure) as

$$L = 0, \text{ for } 0 < t \leq T_0,$$

$$L = \alpha (t - T_0) = L_f (t - T_0) / (T_f - T_0) \text{ for } T_0 < t \leq T_f,$$

$$L = L_f - \beta (t - T_f) = L_f [1 - (t - T_f) / (T_h - T_f)] \text{ for } T_f < t \leq T_h,$$

where L is LAI, t is days after emergence, α is daily LAI increase, T_0 is days from emergence to linear increase of LAI, L_f is maximum LAI around time of flowering (T_f), β is daily LAI decrease, and T_h is days from emergence to harvest.

The LAI change may be better described by a trapezoidal pattern (see figure), but the triangular pattern usually gives a good approximation. If the LAI change is greatly affected by temperature, the LAI change may be better based on accumulated temperature rather than on the number of days. As this can be easily incorporated into the VSM, if necessary, the simplest case as noted above is assumed here.

2. Biomass is accumulated proportionately to the intercepted solar radiation as

$$dW/dt = \epsilon/o [1 - \exp(-kL)],$$

where dW/dt is daily biomass accumulation, E is the light use efficiency, I_0 is incident shortwave radiation, and k is the light extinction coefficient.

3. Yield is denoted as the total biomass at harvest multiplied by the harvest index

$$Y = Wh HI,$$

where Y is grain yield, Wh is total dry weight at harvest, and HI is the harvest index.

Total dry matter is calculated by integrating the daily biomass accumulation. By some approxi-

mations, the integral can be simplified as

$$Wh = \int_0^{T_h} I_0 \epsilon [1 - \exp(-kL)] dt \approx /v \epsilon v \int_0^{T_f} [1 - \exp(-kL)] dt + /r \epsilon r \int_{T_f}^{T_h} [1 - \exp(-kL)] dt$$

$$= /v \epsilon v \{ [1 - [1 - \exp(-k \alpha T_v)] / (k \alpha T_v)] + /r \epsilon r \{ [1 - [1 - \exp(-k \beta T_r)] / (k \beta T_r)] \}$$

$$= \{ 0.85 /v \epsilon v T_v [1 - \exp(-0.55 k \alpha T_v)] + 0.85 /r \epsilon r T_r [1 - \exp(-0.55 k \beta T_r)] \} C,$$

$$= 0.85 [1 - \exp(-0.55 k L_f)] (/v T_v \epsilon v + /r T_r \epsilon r) C,$$

where $T_v = T_f - T_0$, $T_r = T_h - T_f$, $/v$ and $/r$ are the mean daily shortwave radiation for T_v and T_r , respectively, and ϵv and ϵr are the light use efficiency for T_v and T_r , respectively. The factor C accounts for the approximation error. The LAI at flowering (L_f) is not really a parameter, yet it can be easily obtained by measurements or even by guesses.

The crop yield at harvest can, therefore, be expressed as

$$Y \approx HI 0.85 [1 - \exp(-0.55 k L_f)] (/v T_v \epsilon v + /r T_r \epsilon r) C,$$

where Y is yield (g/m^2), HI is the harvest index, k is the light extinction coefficient, L_f is LAI at flowering, $/v$ and $/r$ are the mean daily solar input (MJ/d per m^2) before and after flowering, respectively, T_v is days from the initiation of the linear LAI increase to flowering (d), ϵv and ϵr are the light use efficiency (g/MJ) before and after flowering, respectively, T_r is

Rice yield in Don Daeng village, Thailand. 1981-83.

Year	Yield (g/m^2)		
	Kaida et al (1985)	Miyagawa et al (1985)	VSM
1981	118	182	189
1982	60	NA	154
1983	219	236	266

days from flowering to harvest (d), and C is the correction factor, the full description of which is rather lengthy and, hence, omitted here.

An application: analysis of field survey data. The VSM was applied to the rice yield in Don Daeng Village in northeast Thailand from 1981 to 1983. Most of the VSM parameters, including LAI at flowering, and duration of vegetative and reproductive growth, were estimated from field survey data (Miyagawa 1985, Kaida 1985, Miyagawa and Kuroda 1985), but some were set rather arbitrarily because the data were lacking.

Results of the VSM estimation are in the table. Because of the arbitrariness of setting some parameters, the absolute values of the VSM yield estimate should not be focused upon. The year-to-year variation in yield, however, showed a pattern similar to that of the survey data, with 1983 having the highest yield followed by 1981 and 1982. Further analysis of the survey data suggested poor leaf area development and delayed transplanting as factors contributing to the lower yields in 1981 and 1982 when compared with those in 1983.

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